

Research

Study on the Influence of AI-2/LuxS Quorum Sensing System on the Biofilm Formation of Lactic Acid Bacteria

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Abstract: Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are important probiotic microorganisms used in food fermentation industry. AI-2/LuxS is an important quorum sensing system which affects the growth, biofilm formation, virulence, and metabolism of bacteria. LuxS is encoded by the *luxS* gene, but how AI-2/LuxS is associated with a diverse array of physiological activities in lactic acid bacteria is not known. In this study, four strains of lactic acid bacteria S1-4, among which S1-3 were obtained from Chinese traditional fermented pickles and S4 was the *luxS* gene knockout mutant from the wild strain S1, were used to explore the effect of AI-2/luxS system on the biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria. The results showed that the strains of S1-3 all produced AI-2 signal molecules except S4, but the biofilm formation ability of S4 was the highest among the 4 strains, which demonstrated that the deletion of the *luxS* gene upregulated the biofilm formation ability of S4. Similar results were proven by microscopic observation. It can be seen that the AI-2/LuxS system has a significant impact on biofilm formation. This study will provide the theoretical basis for further research and for the high value of utilization of lactic acid bacteria.

Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria, Biofilm, Quorum sensing system

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Introduction

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are a group of Gram-positive bacteria that can ferment sugars to produce lactic acid^[1]. As one of the most closely related microorganisms to humans, LAB play a crucial role in regulating the microecological balance of the host gut, regulating the immune system, and preventing and treating diseases^[2]. Studies have found that many physiological functions of lactic acid bacteria are closely related to their quorum sensing system, such as competitive adhesion to intestinal pathogens, and the production of bacteriocin. Therefore, studying the quorum sensing system of

lactic acid bacteria can help to better understand the working mechanism of probiotic functions of lactic acid bacteria and expand the application range of lactic acid bacteria.

Quorum Sensing (QS) is a process of intercellular communication that is common in fungi^[3], bacteria, and even viruses^[4]. As an important mechanism for information exchange between bacteria, QS is a gene expression regulation system that depends on bacterial cell density^[5]. It is manifested by releasing specific chemical signal molecules, which are perceived by the bacterial community when their concentration reaches a specific threshold, thereby coordinating the physiological functions of the entire microbial community^[6]. Both G⁺ and G⁻ bacteria use Quorum Sensing^[7]. The signal molecule AI-2 is a common language for intraspecific and interspecific communication among bacteria, and is mainly synthesized by the LuxS protease encoded by the luxS gene in bacteria. Therefore, the AI-2/LuxS quorum sensing system can regulate many physiological functions of bacteria, such as virulence factor production, bioluminescence, biofilm formation, DNA horizontal transfer, extracellular polysaccharide synthesis, cell differentiation, bacterial symbiosis, antibiotic and bacteriocin synthesis, and so on^[8].

Biofilm is an organized bacterial population that adheres to the surface of an object and is surrounded by extracellular macromolecules^[9]. The formation and growth of biofilms are often affected by different factors, such as pH, temperature, relative humidity, surface properties (such as hydrophobicity, wettability, and roughness), nutrient availability, the presence of particulate matter, bacterial strains, and bacterial genomes^[10, 11]. Compared to planktonic cells, biofilm cells are more resistant to antimicrobial agents and have barriers that prevent or reduce contact with antimicrobial agents, which can protect bacteria from osmotic pressure, bacteriophages, toxic compounds, and antibiotics^[12]. In fact, most bacteria grow in the form of biofilms rather than in a floating state^[13].

Although most lactic acid bacteria can form biofilms, biofilms formed by different strains are not the same. The effect of the AI-2/LuxS quorum sensing system on the biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria is unclear. Studies have shown that the formation of lactic acid bacteria biofilms is related to adhesion, which is an important feature of intestinal colonization and probiotic potential of lactic acid bacteria^[14]. Therefore, this study took four strains of lactic acid bacteria as the research object to explore the relationship between biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria and the AI-2/LuxS quorum sensing system, providing new ideas for analyzing the mechanism of biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria and better exerting their probiotic properties.

Materials and methods

1.1 Bacterial strains and culture condition

Three strains of lactic acid bacteria S1, S2, and S3 were isolated from traditional fermented pickles in Hunan Province, China. Strains S1 and S2 were identified as *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* while the strain S3 was identified as *Ligilactobacillus salivarius* using high throughput sequencing. Strain S4 is a luxS gene knockout strain constructed in the laboratory using strain S1 as a template. *Vibrio Campbellii* BB170(ATCC BAA-1117), *Vibrio Campbellii* BB152, and *Escherichia coli* DH5a were provided by Dr. Gu of Inner Mongolia Agricultural University, Inner Mongolia, China. The four strains of lactic acid bacteria were incubated at 37°C for 24h under aerobic conditions in De Man Rogosa & Sharpe (MRS) broth (Haibo Biotechnology Co., Qingdao, China) or on MRS agar. *Vibrio Campbellii* BB152 and *Vibrio Campbellii* BB170 were grown aerobically at 30°C in Luria Bertani (LB) medium (Haibo Biotechnology Co., Qingdao, China) or Marine Broth 2216 medium (Haibo Biotechnology Co., Qingdao, China). *E. coli* strain DH5a was grown at 37°C in LB broth with aeration.

1.2 Cultivation of bacteria and supernatant preparation

The preserved strains of lactic acid bacteria were taken from a refrigerator at - 80°C, inoculated with 0.5% inoculum in MRS agar medium, and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Then single colonies were picked and inoculated in MRS agar medium for 18h.

After activating and culturing the lactic acid bacteria for 2 generations, The LAB strains were inoculated in MRS liquid medium at 37°C for 18 h. The culture supernatants were collected by centrifugation at 6,000 rpm for 10 min, then the supernatants were filtered through a 0.22 µm sterile membrane filters and stored at -80°C in a refrigerator.

1.3 Detection of AI-2

Autoinducer (AI-2) detection assay in minimally processed produce was conducted as described previously^[15] with small modifications. In this experiment, *Vibrio Campbellii* BB170 was used as the reporter strain to verify AI-2 signaling activity. *Vibrio Campbellii* BB170 was cultured in AB medium overnight at 30°C. The cell suspension with an OD₆₀₀ of 0.7-1.2 was diluted with AB medium at 1:100 and shaken evenly for standby. The fresh AB medium and the test bacterial solution were mixed and diluted at a ratio of 1:100. *Vibrio Campbellii* BB152, *Escherichia coli* DH5a, fresh AB medium and MRS medium were served as positive, negative and medium controls, respectively. Two hundred microlitre of the sterile supernatant was added in each well of a 96-well plate. Luminescence was measured at 30°C every 10 min for 0 h and 3.5 h in a fluorescent microtitre plater reader (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Technologies, German). Each sample was measured in at least three independent wells and each data point represents three independent samples. The percentage of AI-2 signaling activity was calculated with RLU with the formula as follow:

$$RLU_{\text{positive}} = \text{positive control mean luminescence} / \text{negative control mean luminescence}$$

$$RLU_{\text{sample}} = \text{sample mean luminescence} / \text{medium control mean luminescence}$$

1.4 Determination of growth and pH of lactic acid bacteria

The four strains of lactic acid bacteria were activated to the second generation, inoculated with 1% inoculum in MRS liquid medium and incubated for 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 hours, respectively. The absorbance value was measured at 600 nm using a spectrophotometer (7200, UNICO (SHANGHAI) INSTRUMENT CO., Shanghai, China) and the pH value was measured using a pH meter (PHS-3C, Shanghai INESA Scientific Instrument Co., Shanghai, China)

1.5 Determination of lactic acid bacteria biofilm production

Biofilm formation assay was performed in 96-well cell culture plates as previously described^[16] with some modifications. Briefly, two hundred microliter MRS broth medium and 2 µL of the diluted bacterial liquid were added to each well of a 96-well plate and incubated at 37°C for 12, 18, 24, and 36 hours, respectively. Further, the planktonic bacteria were aspirated from each well, washed five times with normal saline, dried in an oven and stained with 200 µL 0.2% crystal violet for 15 min. Then the floating color was washed off with normal saline and dried in an oven. Finally, A 4:1 mixture of ethanol and acetone was used for decolorization. The solution was placed on a micro vibrator for 5 minutes, and the absorbance value of OD 600 nm was measured using a multifunctional automatic microplate reader (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Technologies, German). The experiment was carried out in triplicates.

1.6 Microscopic analysis of lactic acid bacteria biofilm

Microscopic analysis of biofilm was performed in 12-well cell culture plates as previously described^[17] with some modifications. Each strain was cultured with 0.1% inoculum in 10 mL of MRS liquid culture medium and shaken evenly for standby. Two milliliter of the culture was added to a 12-well plate, incubated at 37°C for 12, 18, 24, and 36 h, respectively. Then the plate was washed three times with sterilized ultra-pure water and dried in an oven. Two milliliter of 2.5% glutaraldehyde was added to each well and fixed at 4°C for 24 h. The fixed solution was poured out the next day and each well was washed three times with sterilized ultrapure water. Two milliliter of 0.2% crystal violet was added for staining for 20 minutes. Finally, the plate was washed three times with sterilized ultrapure water, and dried in an oven. The biofilm was observed with a microscope (DM500, Leica, German).

1.7 Statistical analysis

Data were evaluated using descriptive statistics and the results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was carried out by SPSS 26.0 (SPSS, IBM Co, Somers, NY, USA) and GraphPad Prism (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, California, USA).

Results and Analysis

2.1 Expression of AI-2 signal molecules in lactic acid bacteria

It can be seen from the analysis in Figure 1 that the relative fluorescence intensity of S1, S2, and S3 is greater than that of the positive control, that is, they can all generate AI-2 signal molecules, making BB170 emit fluorescence, indicating that these three strains of LAB may have the luxS gene. Among them, S1 has the highest relative fluorescence intensity. Compared to the positive control, S4 produces almost no AI-2 signal molecules, and its relative fluorescence intensity value is extremely small.

Fig.1: Expression of AI-2 signal molecules in lactic acid bacteria

2.2 Growth and pH analysis of lactic acid bacteria

According to the analysis in Figure 2, the growth of S1 is generally larger than the other three strains, but there is no significant difference between S1 and S4. The pH of the four strains showed no significant difference and tended to stabilize after 20 h. This indicates that the AI-2/LuxS system has no significant effect on the growth and pH change of S1.

Fig.2: Growth and pH curve of lactic acid bacteria

2.3 Biofilm production of lactic acid bacteria

Lactic acid bacteria are a type of gram-positive bacteria, and crystal violet can penetrate into the cell wall. However, gram-positive bacteria have thicker cell walls and dense peptidoglycan interconnections, so crystal violet binds tightly to the cell wall and is not easily washed out. Currently, crystal violet staining is still one of the classic methods for measuring the production of biofilms. Crystal violet is adsorbed by the cell wall. After removing the floating color, a mixture of ethanol and acetone is added to the pore plate, and then shaken with a micro oscillator to fully elute crystal violet. At this time, the OD600 value of the solution represents the amount of biofilm produced by the bacterium.

From the analysis in Figure 3, it can be seen that the amount of biofilm formation of S1 before 18 h was less, after 24 hours, it slightly increased, and reached the highest level at 36 h. S4 produced a small amount of biofilm at 12 h, then rose sharply at 18 and 24 h, reaching a peak of 1.161 ± 0.085 at 24 h. After 36 h, the biofilm fell off, and the absorbance

decreased to 0.561 ± 0.029 . The growth rate of S2 is similar to that of S3, reaching a peak at 24 h and decreasing at 36 h, but only at 24 h does the value of S2 decrease compared to the value of S3. It can be seen that under the same inoculation amount at different times, these four strains of lactic acid bacteria have their own biofilm growth trend.

According to the analysis in Figure 3, there is a significant difference in the amount of biofilm formation between S1 and S4. The amount of biofilm formation of S4 has always been higher than that of S1, indicating that the luxS gene can regulate the biofilm formation of S1. Knocking out the luxS gene can instead enhance the biofilm formation ability of S1, which means the AI-2/LuxS system negatively regulates the ability of biofilm formation in S1.

Fig.3: Biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria in different time periods

2.4 Microscopic analysis of lactic acid bacteria biofilm

Fig.4: Micrographs of lactic acid bacteria biofilms (400 x)

From the analysis of the following diagrams, it can be seen that under the inverted microscope, the formation stages of biofilms can correspond one to one. In the microscopic image of S4, 12h is the stage of biofilm regulating membrane formation and cell adhesion, 18h is the stage of rapid formation of microflora, filling a large number of gaps on the surface of the object, and 24h is the stage of maturity of the biofilm, forming a 3D three-dimensional structure on the surface of the object. After 36h, due to limited space and nutrition, competition between cells cannot continue to grow well, resulting in the shedding of the biofilm. This special form of bacterial aggregation wants to leave the environment and find new locations to survive. At the same time, the comparison between the biofilm microscopic analysis in Figure 4 and the biofilm formation amount of S4 in Figure 3 shows that the formation amount of S4 biofilm also follows this trend, increasing from 12 hours to the highest level in 24 hours, and decreasing due to malnutrition at 36 hours. Based on the microscopic analysis of S1, it can be seen that the biofilm did not mature at 12, 18, and 24 hours, until a relatively three-dimensional biofilm appeared at 36 hours, and the gaps on the surface of the object were almost covered. In the microscopic images of S2 and S3, at 12 h, the surface of the object was already covered with biofilm, and the subsequent images were almost the same. It may be that the ability to form a three-dimensional biological film is weak and cannot form a thicker part, but the ability to adhere to the surface of the object is strong and there are not many gaps. Microscopic analysis of the biofilms of S1 and S4 shows that the AI-2/LuxS system has a negative regulatory effect on S1. The AI-2/LuxS system can affect the maturation of the biofilm of S1, resulting in a significant lag in biofilm formation.

Conclusion

This study measured the biofilm formation ability of four strains of lactic acid bacteria, demonstrating that the AI-2/LuxS system has a regulatory effect on biofilm formation of lactic acid bacteria. Strain S4, as a luxS gene knockout strain of S1, produces almost no AI-2 signal molecules, but its biofilm formation is the largest, indicating a negative correlation between luxS gene expression and biofilm formation in lactic acid bacteria. Microscopic analysis also showed that S4 had the thickest biofilm.

This was also found in the microscopic analysis of biofilms, the most obvious of which was that within 24 h, the S4 biofilm had almost covered the entire surface of the object, in which it had been thickened to varying degrees, forming a relatively three-dimensional biofilm structure. However, S1 still had large gaps and did not fully adhere to the surface of the object, which was easily dispersed, and the remaining biofilm was not thickened. It can be seen that the AI-2/LuxS system has a significant impact on biofilm formation. Although S4 knocks out the luxS gene and cannot produce AI-2 signaling molecules, its biofilm formation ability is higher than that of the original strain S1.

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